

Undergraduate mathematics students' views on assessed group work

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Previous research has examined the implementation of collaborative learning and the conditions under which it may be optimally effective. One means of implementing collaborative learning in the university setting is through assessed group work, whereby students are asked to work together to submit a piece of coursework for assessment. In the context of undergraduate mathematics, assessed group work is a relatively novel means of assessment, and previous research has documented undergraduate mathematics students' preference for the retention of the status quo of assessment through closed-book examinations. This paper builds on previous research, related to both collaborative learning and assessment, by examining undergraduate mathematics students' views on assessed group work. To this end, semi-structured, one-to-one, interviews were conducted with ten recent graduates from undergraduate degrees in the mathematical sciences. Data analysis was conducted using reflexive thematic analysis. Findings indicate an uncertainty among students as to the purpose of implementing assessed group work in undergraduate mathematics degrees. Additionally, participants demonstrated concern regarding the assessment and allocation of groups in any proposed implementation of assessed group work. We discuss potential implications for practice, highlighting the importance of considering students' views when evaluating and implementing alternative assessment methods.

Keywords: Assessed group work, Collaborative learning, Assessment, Undergraduate mathematics education

Introduction

While there is no well-established definition of collaborative learning, we will follow the broad conceptualisation of Johnson et al. (2014) and define it to be a set of methods in which students “work together to maximize their own and each other’s learning” (p. 87). Much of the research which has been conducted on collaborative learning to date has focused on its implementation and evaluating the conditions under which it might be optimally effective (e.g., Johnson et al., 2007; Springer et al., 1999). One means of implementing collaborative learning in a university context is through assessed group work, whereby students are asked to work together to submit a piece of coursework for assessment.

Undergraduate mathematics degrees in the UK and Ireland, the setting of this study, are predominantly assessed through closed-book examination (Iannone & Simpson, 2011, 2022; National Forum for the Enhancement of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education [National Forum], 2016). This means that assessed group work is a rather novel concept for an undergraduate mathematics student. Previous research, examining undergraduate mathematics students' perceptions of oral performance assessment (Iannone & Simpson, 2015b), has advocated for the representation of students' views when evaluating and implementing alternative assessment methods. We hope to add to research on undergraduate mathematics students' assessment preferences, and collaborative learning in the context of mathematics, by addressing our research question: ‘What are undergraduate mathematics students' views on assessed group work?’.

Literature Review

Slavin (1996) remarked that it could be considered a point of irony that researchers who have examined aspects of collaborative learning have “often operated in isolation from one another, almost on parallel tracks” (p. 44). There is no singular, well-established definition of collaborative learning and different researchers have focused on various aspects in their analyses of the issue (Slavin, 1996). However, we will follow the broad conceptualisation of Johnson et al. (2014), defining collaborative learning as encompassing a set of methods in which students “work together to maximize their own and each other’s learning” (p. 87). We additionally distinguish assessed group work as lecturer-mandated group work where students work together to submit a piece of coursework for assessment.

Previous research conducted on collaborative learning has generally focused on the implementation of collaborative instructional methods by teachers and lecturers, evaluating their effects and the conditions under which they may be optimally effective (e.g., Johnson et al., 2007; Springer et al., 1999). Slavin (1996) outlines four broad types of theoretical perspectives from which researchers can come to the issue of collaborative learning: motivational, social cohesion, developmental, and cognitive elaboration. Each perspective places emphasis on different aspects of collaboration between students, and this is reflected in researchers’ recommendations for the implementation of collaborative learning. The focus of motivational perspectives is primarily on the “reward or goal structures under which students operate” (Slavin, 1996, p. 44), and places emphasis on all group members feeling a sense of individual accountability to the group. Social cohesion perspectives are concerned with the importance of positive interpersonal relationships between peers and contend that when students feel a connection with one another, learning and peer-teaching occurs as a natural consequence. The emphasis of developmental perspectives is on the learning which results from the resolution of cognitive conflicts and, as a result, promotes opportunities for students to share and hear opposing viewpoints. Adopters of a cognitive elaboration perspective believe that an effective means for students to learn is through “explaining the material to someone else” (Slavin, 1996, p. 50) and emphasise peer-teaching as a result.

Much of the research referenced above relates to a general educational context. Research on students’ assessment preferences has demonstrated the importance of not automatically accepting findings from the general education literature as valid in a mathematical context (Iannone & Simpson, 2015a). Closed-book examinations are the primary means of assessment in undergraduate mathematics degrees in the UK and Ireland (Iannone & Simpson, 2011, 2022; National Forum, 2016). In spite of a general tendency, documented in the general education literature, for students to prefer less traditional forms of assessment, undergraduate mathematics students appear to favour the retention of the status quo of assessment, primarily, through closed-book examinations (Iannone & Simpson, 2015a). Students were found to prefer, and deem most fair, assessment methods they perceived as being best able to distinguish between *individual* students’ mathematical proficiencies. To that end, it was found that “any assessment that can be completed in groups...may be deemed to be unfair” (Iannone & Simpson, 2015a, p. 1058). Additionally, some mathematics students have exhibited concern regarding the possibility of other

students' performance impacting their grade in the context of assessed group work (Iannone & Simpson, 2017).

While little is known about undergraduate mathematics students' engagement in, and perceptions of, collaboration in the context of mathematics, mathematicians' views on the issue have been documented to a greater extent. The collaborative nature of mathematics emerged as a prominent theme in the work of Burton (1999), who conducted an interview-based study with 70 mathematicians from the UK and Ireland. In contrast to the often-purported image of the solitary mathematician, only four of the 70 interviewed mathematicians reported working on mathematics entirely alone and many spoke of a cultural shift towards a collaborative norm.

Methodology

As the aim of this study is to understand undergraduate mathematics students' views on, and experiences of, collaborating with their peers, a descriptive phenomenological design was chosen. One-on-one, semi-structured interviews were conducted in spring 2022 with ten recent graduates (graduating in 2019, 2020 and 2021) from degrees in the mathematical sciences from a large, Irish university. Initially, graduates known to the authors were invited to participate. From there a form of snowball sampling was used, with recruited participants asked to recommend other graduates who may be interested in participating. We sought participants' views on both assessed group work and informal, voluntary collaboration with peers undertaken outside of their lectures and tutorials. The interviews, which were conducted by the first author and lasted on average 30 minutes, were audio-recorded and transcribed.

We undertook reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2022) based on descriptive phenomenology in a manner which was guided by Sundler et al. (2019). We were particularly guided by their discussion of paying attention to the importance of researchers recognising and questioning any "personal beliefs, theories or other assumptions that can restrict the researcher's openness", rather than "attempting to set aside one's experiences and assumptions" (Sundler et al., 2019, p. 735). At the time of data collection, the first author was a final-year undergraduate mathematics student and, having had personal experience of working with peers on group assessments, would be considered an insider researcher (Braun & Clarke, 2022). The second author is a mathematics lecturer and mathematics education researcher. The method's emphasis on researcher reflexivity allowed for these two disparate perspectives to be capitalised on and used as a "resource for knowledge production [...] rather than a must-be-contained threat to credibility" (Braun & Clarke, 2021, pp. 334-335).

Braun and Clarke's (2022) six-stage process was followed. In line with Braun and Clarke (2022), the second author took on the role of an "experienced qualitative researcher [and] supervisor" (p. 273), both participating in and supporting the first author in the analysis process. Both authors familiarised themselves with the data corpus through repeated reading of the interview transcripts and re-listening to the audio-recordings. Throughout this process, notes were made on any initial ideas, and both authors wrote reflections on their position in relation to the data and topic. For the purposes of this paper, our research question is

concerned with participants' perceptions of assessed group work. Therefore, the data set which was then coded became "all instances in the corpus where that topic is referred" (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 79). This data set was coded by the first author using the software package NVivo. An inductive approach was taken, and no pre-existing theoretical framework was used. However, the first author was aware that her coding was likely influenced by prior reading of literature on assessment and collaboration and the issues highlighted therein. A mixture of semantic and more latent codes was used. For instance, while the code 'Individual marks don't really work' captures an explicit, overt meaning in the data, the code 'Different students have different goals' centred on the more implicit narrative that students should be free to work towards their own individual goals.

The first author then reviewed her codes and associated data extracts and wrote a short analytic summary of each. She then began to sort the code labels into candidate themes, which were explored in relation to one another and the entire data set, using visual thematic mappings. Through this process, focusing on whether there was something different about group assessment in mathematics as opposed to other subjects, she decided that a candidate theme was under-developed as it was not addressed fully enough in the data. The remaining three themes were then named and defined, and a final visual thematic mapping produced.

Findings

Existing research has identified closed-book examinations as the prevalent assessment method in undergraduate mathematics degrees in the UK and Ireland (Iannone & Simpson, 2011, 2022; National Forum, 2016). This is reflected in the fact that the mathematics graduates interviewed as part of this study reported limited experience of group assessment. Their experiences of assessed group work were largely confined to a small number of group projects, mainly statistics and programming related, completed in various modules, and the option, in a few instances, to submit problem sheets as a group as opposed to individually. In order to address our research question, participants were asked for their views on assessed group work based on their own limited experience and were also asked to respond to the hypothetical proposal of assessed group work being made a larger component of the 'assessment diet' in undergraduate mathematics. This paper reports three themes in relation to our research question: 'Is the purpose, necessarily, to learn more mathematics?', 'Not when my grade depends on it', and 'Navigating freedom and fairness in relation to group composition'.

A scepticism among participants as to whether group work has direct benefits to students' mathematical learning became the focus of the theme 'Is the purpose, necessarily, to learn more mathematics?'. This was particularly evident in discussions regarding the prospect of 'divvying up' work among group members in mathematics. For instance, some participants mentioned that when asked to complete a problem sheet as a group, perhaps the most obvious approach would be to divide up the relevant questions among group members. However, some participants did not deem this suitable in the context of mathematics. They felt it important that they understand all questions on a problem sheet, rather than just a subset: "If four of us do one question each, then I don't feel like I know how to do the other

three questions” (Graduate 9). Other participants spoke of issues arising when each of the constituent group member’s questions were checked prior to submission:

It was mainly me checking their work to be honest. So I checked [another student’s] work and then unfortunately there were a bunch of errors and issues with it that we then kind of needed to fix quickly. (Graduate 3)

Graduate 3’s account implicitly raises the issue of heterogeneous student abilities in group assessments. Some participants deemed the purpose, and perhaps the value, of group work as allowing for the “delegat[ion of] some of the teaching” (Graduate 1) and effectively to:

Get some stronger students and weaker students to work together and maybe the stronger students can learn by having to teach other people and the weaker students can learn from both the lecturer and the other students. (Graduate 3)

There was no concrete consensus as to whether assessed group work definitively benefits all students’ learning and a number of participants hypothesised about whether the decision to implement assessed group work might stem from a place of pragmatism, in relation to grading, on the part of lecturers. Some participants did speak to the value they saw in group work in providing an opportunity for students to learn to work with others: “I’m not sure you necessarily learn more maths by submitting as a group, but I think you probably learn more skills, life skills as it were” (Graduate 4).

The value they saw in peer-teaching and in learning life skills meant that some graduates were not entirely opposed to the concept of assessed group work. However, many approached the prospect with a degree of apprehension. Their concerns, in relation to the assessment of group work, became the focus of the theme ‘Not when my grade depends on it’. A recurring sentiment was that individual student’s ambitions, in relation to assessment, ought to be respected. However, as Graduate 8 illustrates, tension can arise when individual student’s goals are in conflict with one another: “some people [...] are happy enough to get a certain grade and that’s completely fine, but it’s not fair throwing them in with someone who wants to do better”. The dilemma of how to reconcile heterogeneous student goals and ambitions appeared to lie at the heart of some students’ issues with assessed group work: “There’s two outcomes, either it’s one or two people in the group working really hard that like, get everybody an A+ or it just brings everybody closer to an average” (Graduate 8).

Also relevant to the above theme were participants’ discussions of how inequity in student workload can lead to conflict and feelings of resentment. It was felt by some participants that, *if* assessed group work were to be implemented, there should be some means of ensuring, or incentivising, individual members to be accountable to the group. Some suggestions included implementing a system of individual marks, or individual interviews between students and the lecturer in order to gauge understanding. As Graduate 1 phrased it, it was felt there ought to be “some reward for actually trying”. However, some participants also expressed doubts as to the feasibility of implementing such mechanisms. While some felt that group work has the potential to be “super, super helpful” (Graduate 6), the graduates appeared dubious as to whether it would be possible to assuage their concerns in relation to assessment. Graduate 1 summarises this sentiment, saying “if there is a way of kind of preventing that, then I think it is really good. But I don’t know what that would be”.

It is possible to argue that many of the aforementioned student concerns regarding assessed group work seem to stem from assigned, heterogeneous student groupings. The issue of group composition forms the cornerstone of the theme ‘Navigating freedom and fairness in relation to group composition’. While the informal collaboration that students voluntarily engage in is beyond the scope of this paper, some graduates did contrast their experiences of assessed group work with a certain sense of freedom experienced in their informal collaborations. Graduate 8 discusses the flexibility, in the informal case, of being able to work with others if you wish but “if you don’t then it’s not like affecting anyone else either. It’s just your grade”. Others discussed a sense of ease in working with peers who you know well:

[Assessed group work] was more kind of stilted because you didn’t know the people. When it was informal, you knew the people, everything flowed pretty easily. There was kind of an unwritten routine. (Graduate 7)

In spite of this, only two graduates reported being in favour of letting students self-select their own groups in the context of assessed group work. A number of participants deemed the prospect unfair, their reasons falling broadly into two categories. Some graduates felt that students were likely to pick their “smartest friends” (Graduate 2) and believed that it did not “seem like a very fair approach to [...] group people together by levels and tell them to work together on something they are going to be graded on” (Graduate 9). Others worried about potential social implications, and how “people in the module who didn’t know anyone else” (Graduate 7) may be unfairly disadvantaged. It was also felt that assigned, heterogeneous groups were reflective of the nature of collaboration students may be expected to engage in later in life. These beliefs are seemingly at odds with difficulties encountered when working in assigned groups, and the freedom experienced when working with peers in an informal setting. This apparent tension is captured by Graduate 8 who ponders:

It’s a funny thing because [...] if you don’t get to pick your groups then you’re put with people who want to work differently. But if you just pick like, in essence I guess we kind of just picked our own group that was quite strong and then did well because of that so [...] yeah, I’m not sure. (Graduate 8)

Discussion

For those seeking an answer to the question of whether assessed group work has a role to play in undergraduate mathematics education, this paper offers no clear answers. However, our findings do suggest that any implementation of assessed group work requires careful thought, consideration, and an evaluation as to the purpose it is to serve. We, along with Iannone and Simpson (2015b), advocate that any such evaluation “should take into account the views of students” (p. 983), on which this paper does shed some light.

As previously outlined, the interviewed graduates questioned whether there are direct benefits of assessed group work to students’ mathematical learning. Adopters of a developmental perspective assert that “interaction among students on learning tasks will lead *in itself* to improved student achievement” (Slavin, 1996, p. 49). They emphasise learning through the resolution of cognitive conflicts which arise in students’ discussion of content. This diverges from our participants’ depiction of the process of dividing problem sheet

questions among group members and the role of checking each member's contribution, in some cases, falling to one student. Research on students' assessment preferences has highlighted the importance of not automatically accepting findings from the general education literature as valid in a mathematical context. While not explicitly addressed in this paper we, along with Slavin (1996), highlight the need for "research at the intersection of cooperative learning and curriculum" (p. 62) in order to examine whether there is something different about assessed group work in the context of mathematics, as opposed to in other subjects.

Some graduates suggested that a potential purpose of implementing assessed group work could be encouraging students to engage in peer-teaching. This aligns with a cognitive elaboration perspective (Slavin, 1996) on collaborative learning. Slavin asserts the importance of rewarding a group based on the learning of its individual members in order to encourage students to engage with the group and to help one another. He argues against rewarding groups on the basis of a product which "could theoretically have been done by one group member" (Slavin, 1996, p. 54), as is the case with students working together to submit a problem sheet, and stresses that each group member should see their own personal success as inseparably linked to the success of the group. Relevant here is the graduates' discussion of the perceived inequity of a student feeling compelled to do additional work in order to compensate for differences in individual member's goals in relation to assessment. This raises interesting points to be considered by lecturers with a view to implementing assessed group work. Do they view the purpose of assessed group work as, in the words of one participant, allowing for the delegation of some of the teaching and, if so, how do they perceive the applicability of Slavin's thesis to an undergraduate mathematical context?

This paper also contributes to our understanding of students' preferences in relation to the assessment of undergraduate mathematics. Complementing the work of Iannone and Simpson (2015a, 2015b, 2017), it demonstrates that students' views in relation to assessment are thoughtful and nuanced, and ought to be considered in the evaluation and implementation of alternative assessment methods. As reported by Iannone and Simpson (2015a, 2017), participants in our study also indicated a preference for the assessment of their *individual* mathematical ability. They additionally exhibited concern regarding the allocation of groups and the assessment of any potential implementation of assessed group work. We therefore advocate for these two areas of concern to be addressed explicitly with students in any implementation of assessed group work in undergraduate mathematics degrees.

Finally, although beyond the scope of this paper we note some participants' favourable discussions of their engagement in informal collaboration with peers, outside the context of assessed group work. Of particular interest is the apparent alleviation of concerns regarding assessment and unfamiliar, heterogenous groups. Noting Burton's (1999) mathematicians' depiction of mathematics as a collaborative discipline, we hope to examine mathematics students' engagement in informal collaboration further in our wider study.

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